

INCOME INEQUALITY, OUT-OF-POCKET HEALTH EXPENDITURE AND HEALTH OUTCOME IN SELECTED AFRICAN COUNTRIES

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Abstract

The study examined the effect of income inequality and out-of-pocket (OOP) health expenditure on health outcomes, proxy by the Under-5 mortality rate, in selected economies in Africa, inclusive of South Africa, Egypt, Algeria, Nigeria and Ethiopia. The increasing financial hardship in accessing necessary medical care, due to the government's inability to fulfill its healthcare financing obligations among many African countries has raised serious concern regarding the consequential outcomes. In analyzing the effect of income inequality and Out of Pocket (OOP) health expenditure on health outcome, using dataset obtained both from World Development Indicators (WDI) and World Income Inequality Database (WIID), we constructed ARDL-PMG model following the outcomes of unit root test. The outcomes of the analysis show that none of the independent variables has significant effect on under-five mortality rate in the short run. However, in the long run, both Gini index and OOP demonstrate positive significant effect on under-five mortality rate while Health expenditure and GDP per capita show negative significant effect. Thus, the findings suggest that the policymakers in these countries should prioritize long-term measures to reduce income inequality and promote accessible healthcare financing to improve health outcomes

Keywords: Out of Pocket, Under-Five Mortality, Income Inequality, ARDL, Health Outcome

1.1 Background to the Study

Despite being among the largest economies in Africa, Nigeria, Egypt, Algeria, South Africa, and Ethiopia still struggle with healthcare financing. Income inequality and reliance on OOP payments significantly affect health outcomes. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2021), a relatively small proportion of their increased budgets was allocated to the health sector, with most additional resources directed toward social protection and economic stabilisation efforts. World Bank (2016) asserts that historically, low-income countries (LICs), the majority of which are in sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia, have consistently allocated less to healthcare compared to middle- and high-income countries (HICs). The statistics from the WHO (2021) reveal that the global average health spending per capita was \$1,105 in 2019. In stark contrast, the average per capita health expenditure was just \$39 in LICs, compared to \$3,191 in high-income countries (HICs). The same report estimates that for LMICS to achieve the health targets outlined in Sustainable Development Goal (SDGS) 3 by 2030, they will need to increase their healthcare spending to approximately \$41 per capita. This figure exceeds current spending levels, which are around \$31 per person. Evidence suggests that financial flows within African health systems exacerbate inefficiencies and inequities, with funds disproportionately allocated to urban areas and specialised care. If these trends persist and key issues in health financing across the continent are not addressed, the recent progress in reducing mortality rates for diseases such as HIV, malaria, and measles is at risk of being reversed (WHO, 2013).

In healthcare financing, several mechanisms can be explored, including government budgetary spending, pooled risk insurance schemes, foreign aid, and out-of-pocket (OOP) payments. In most advanced economies, these mechanisms function complementarily rather than dependently on one another. Government spending, however, typically constitutes the largest share of health expenditure in HICs (Zouhar et al, 2021). This observation aligns with findings from the WHO (2021), which indicates that across middle- and high-income countries, the proportion of health spending financed through domestic public sources has increased over the past two decades, accompanied by a corresponding decline in reliance on OOP payments. This trend suggests a progressive shift in health financing towards compulsory prepaid sources, such as general government budgets and mandatory health insurance contributions, although per capita OOP spending has continued to rise. On the contrary, research has shown that in LICs, the share of government expenditure allocated to health has been steadily declining, while external aid and OOP payments are increasing. For instance, a report by the World Bank (2016) indicates that government health expenditure in the African region has declined in half of the countries in the region and that only four countries met the Abuja target of 15 percent general expenditure as of 2014.

The rise in foreign aid to these countries has, paradoxically, led to a reduction in government health spending, compounded by the fact that insurance systems in these regions are often inadequate and inefficient. While external aid is intended to complement, rather than replace, domestic health expenditure, many LICs, including Nigeria, Egypt, Morocco, South Africa, Algeria, and Ethiopia,

have surpassed the government health spending (Zouhar *et al.*, 2021; Reem, 2018). This raises concerns about the sustainability and self-reliance of healthcare financing in these nations. Uzonwanne, et al (2022) observed that the key health initiatives implemented by the federal government in Nigeria, for instance, have failed to achieve their primary objective of making affordable healthcare accessible to the population. The underlying reason for this failure is good ideas alone are insufficient; successful outcomes require effective implementation and action. Nigeria, like many of its African counterparts, remains heavily reliant on foreign aid and private spending to finance its healthcare system. According to the WHO (2021), Nigeria was among the top five recipients of external health aid globally in 2019, alongside Ethiopia, Tanzania, Kenya, and Mozambique. Notably, Nigeria emerged as the largest recipient, receiving \$1.1 billion in health aid, which constituted 6.5% of global external health aid. In addition to external health aid, another prominent component of healthcare financing in Nigeria is out-of-pocket (OOP) expenditure, which continues to play a substantial role in healthcare spending.

Due to the government's inability to fulfill its healthcare financing obligations, a significant portion of the African population continues to experience financial hardship in accessing necessary medical care. Several studies (Aregbeshola & Khan, 2018; Opeloyeru, 2024; World Bank, 2016) have established a high reliance on OOP payments as the primary means of healthcare financing in many African countries. Yara et al (2020) and Opeloyeru (2024) observe that OOP payments can significantly reduce disposable income, contributing to the persistence of poverty among households over time. Similarly, World Bank (2016) argues that due to increasing OOP payments, nearly 11 million Africans are falling into poverty. The Pan American Health Organization (PAHO, 2021) argues that OOP payments are among the most inefficient and inequitable methods of financing healthcare systems as they disproportionately burden households and individuals, often forcing them to choose between essential needs—such as education, food, and housing—and spending on healthcare to save loved ones from illness, suffering, or premature death. Similarly, WHO (2021) notes that OOP health expenditures can impose financial hardship, particularly when they surpass a predefined threshold of a household's ability to pay, leading to difficult choices between healthcare and other necessities. According to Ewurum, et al (2020), OOP payments can create a scenario where many households are constrained from accessing essential medical treatments, as they must allocate a significant portion of their income for healthcare. In many cases, households face the risk of foregoing medical treatment when confronted with financial strain, often leading to near impoverishment.

As noted by WHO (2016), 32% of global healthcare expenditure comes from out-of-pocket (OOP) payments. From 2000 to 2019, OOP spending represented 44% of health expenditure in low-income countries (LICs), while external aid contributed 29%. In these countries, OOP spending by households grew at a faster rate than overall household consumption, increasing the share of household budgets allocated to healthcare from 3.1% in 2000 to 3.5% in 2019 (WHO, 2021). The World Bank (2016) reports that OOP payments have risen significantly across most African countries, with regional averages increasing from \$15 per capita in 1995 to \$38 in 2014. In Egypt, OOP payments accounted for about 70% of healthcare spending between 2008 and 2009. By 2016,

this figure declined to 62%, though Egypt remained one of the countries with the highest OOP health payments in the region (Yara *et al.*, 2020). In Nigeria, OOP payments account for approximately 75% of total healthcare expenditure (Opeloyeru, 2024).

Income inequality can have profound implications for health outcomes. Despite periods of economic growth and increased government spending in some selected African countries (Nigeria, Egypt, Ethiopia, Algeria and South Africa), the benefits of these advancements have not been equitably distributed across the population, resulting in enduring health disparities (Samuel *et al.*, 2018). The persistence of both income inequality and elevated OOP payment presents substantial challenges to improving health outcomes in the LICs. This pronounced income inequality has been shown to adversely impact health outcomes (Angbas *et al.*, 2018). Chrys, *et al.* (2022) further emphasise that in contexts of high-income inequality, a substantial proportion of low-income individuals are more susceptible to increased exposure, transmission, and mortality during health crises. This observation aligns with Odusanya and Agboola's (2017) assertion that low-income individuals are particularly vulnerable to adverse health conditions. While the relationship between health outcomes and health financing is complex and not necessarily linear, evidence suggests that the structure of healthcare financing significantly influences access to healthcare, which, in turn, impacts health outcomes. This aligns with the arguments presented by Godwin *et al.* (2023); and Uzochukwu and Uju (2012), who attribute poor health outcomes in LICs, e.g., Nigeria, to the government's insufficient contribution to health spending. Furthermore, it supports the conclusions drawn by Odusanya *et al.* (2017) and Orekoya (2022), which highlight that despite Nigeria's status as one of Africa's largest economies, its health outcomes, such as life expectancy, infant mortality, and under-5 mortality rates, remain strikingly unimpressive. World Bank (2016) made a similar observation regarding Egypt, Algeria, Ethiopia and South Africa.

However, World Bank (2016) links economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) to poverty reduction and, subsequently, a gain in health outcomes. According to the report, between 1990 and 2015, SSA witnessed a 57 percent child mortality rate, and the maternal mortality ratio (MMR) fell by 45 percent. This progress is claimed to have been enabled by economic growth. Relying on this assertion, we are motivated to examine how income inequality and OOP health expenditure affect health outcomes in the selected African economies comprising South Africa, Egypt, Algeria, Nigeria and Ethiopia. According to the information published on its official website, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) ranked these five economies as the largest in Africa according to the 2024 ranking. South Africa maintains the lead GDP of \$373.23 billion, followed by Egypt whose GDP stands at \$347.69 billion, then Algeria with a GDP of \$266.78 billion. The GDPs of Nigeria and Ethiopia are \$252.74 billion and \$192 billion, respectively. Further justifying our position on the selection of these countries as our target of study, a report by Africa HR Solutions identifies three of the countries, namely, South Africa, Egypt and Nigeria, as the destinations for healthcare investments in the African continent. These countries have large populations with healthcare spending potential, increased government participation in initiatives and medical reforms to reshape the medical landscape in their countries and thriving pharmaceutical industries

springing up in these countries. The question will be how all these factors have reduced OOP health expenditures.

1.2 Literature Review

Empirical findings reveal diverse perspectives among scholars regarding the relationships among income inequality, OOP health expenditures, and health outcomes. While some studies assert a direct relationship among these variables, others challenge this view. Below are several studies relevant to this investigation. Rezwani et al (2018) employed partial least squares regression, based on a structural equation model, to construct a health outcome index for 30 OECD countries from 2004 to 2015. Their findings indicate that income inequality has a detrimental effect on health outcomes. Furthermore, the study highlighted that OECD countries with a higher proportion of publicly funded healthcare demonstrate better public health outcomes compared to those with a smaller share of public healthcare funding. Similarly, Shuangshuang and Bin (2021) explored the impact of income inequality on health outcomes across emerging Asian economies from 1991 to 2019. Their results show a negative long-term effect of income inequality on life expectancy. The study also found that increases in income inequality contributed to a decline in life expectancy, whereas decreases in inequality led to improvements in life expectancy over the long term in these economies. The study, therefore, emphasises the need for governments to carefully assess the impact of their economic policies on income inequality to improve health outcomes.

Pamela, María, and Paul (2022) utilised probit models with a pooled cross-sectional dataset to examine the impact of income inequality on individual health status in Colombia. Their findings suggest that residing in regions with higher average income reduces the likelihood of experiencing poor health. Additionally, the study revealed that individuals who finance their healthcare are less likely to report poor health, whereas those relying on government-subsidised healthcare are more likely to experience poor health outcomes. In other words, individuals who rely on OOP healthcare expenditures tend to report better health than those dependent on government healthcare services. Similarly, Odusanya and Akinlo (2021), who explored the relationship between income inequality and health across 31 Sub-Saharan African countries, report that higher income inequality is associated with lower life expectancy, reflecting its negative impact on overall life span. In a related study, Odusanya *et al.* (2017) investigated the effects of income and income inequality on health in Nigeria between 1980 and 2014, employing the ARDL Bounds testing approach to assess both long- and short-term impacts. The results showed that income has a significant positive relationship with health outcomes in the long and short run. Conversely, income inequality has a significant positive effect on infant mortality, indicating that higher inequality is associated with increased infant mortality rates in both the short and long term in Nigeria.

Orekoya (2022) conducted an empirical analysis of the relationship between income inequality and health status in Nigeria. Utilizing variables such as life expectancy, public health expenditure, infant mortality, the Gini coefficient, gross fixed capital formation, household per capita, final consumption, gross national income, and transfer payments, the study employed the autoregressive distributed lags (ARDL) technique for data analysis. The findings indicate a short-run equilibrium

between income inequality and health indicators, including life expectancy, public health expenditure, and infant mortality. However, overall, the results show that income inequality significantly influences health outcomes when assessed through public health expenditure, but not when life expectancy and infant mortality are indicators. The study further suggests that the drivers of income inequality in Nigeria are primarily non-health factors, particularly aggregate investment, transfer payments, and overall economic growth. Ajayi *et al.* (2021) employed a multistage sampling technique to investigate the burden of OOP health expenditures among households in selected rural and urban areas of Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study found that the prevalence of catastrophic health expenditure is significantly higher in rural areas compared to urban areas. While the prevalence of catastrophic health expenditure is a notable concern across Nigeria, it is particularly acute in rural regions. Consequently, the authors recommend that policymakers establish financial and social intervention mechanisms to protect households from catastrophic health expenditures. In another study, Ewurum *et al.* (2020) utilised three-stage least squares estimators to analyse the effects of public and household health expenditures on economic development in Nigeria. The empirical results indicate that public health expenditure does not have a statistically significant impact on economic development. In contrast, household out-of-pocket health expenditures demonstrate a substantial positive effect on the country's economic development. This indicates the need for public authorities to implement policies aimed at enhancing household incomes, thereby improving access to quality healthcare. Such measures could increase productivity potential and contribute to higher national income.

Abdalla and Norashidah (2021) utilized a dynamic panel threshold technique to explore the relationship between out-of-pocket (OOP) health expenditure and poverty in 145 countries from 2000 to 2017. The results indicate that, for lower-income countries below the threshold for OOP health expenditure, the effect on poverty reduction was either positive or insignificant. In contrast, exceeding this threshold was associated with an increase in poverty. The authors conclude that improving healthcare systems by maintaining manageable levels of OOP health expenditure is a crucial step toward achieving better health coverage and poverty reduction in many developing nations. Similarly, Godwin *et al.* (2023) investigated the impact of household OOP spending and health shocks on poverty in Nigeria. The study employed least squares regression to estimate both short-run error correction models and long-run effects. The findings reveal a significant negative impact of OOP expenditures and malaria incidence rates on real income per capita and secondary school enrollment. Conversely, life expectancy demonstrated a significant positive effect on both real income per capita and secondary school enrollment. However, the maternal mortality rate was found to have an insignificant impact on these outcomes. The study concludes that to effectively reduce poverty, the government should enhance financial protection, improve maternal health services, combat malaria, and strengthen healthcare infrastructure.

Oladimeji and Adewale (2022) investigated the impact of income inequality and healthcare expenditure on economic performance in Nigeria. Employing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) estimation technique, the study found a positive and statistically significant relationship between income inequality and economic performance, as well as healthcare expenditure and

economic performance in Nigeria. Consequently, the authors conclude that implementing programs and policies aimed at reducing income inequality, alongside macroeconomic policies focused on public health expenditure, is essential for enhancing economic performance in the country. In a related study, Ogunjimi and Adebayo (2018) utilized the Toda-Yamamoto causality framework and ARDL Bounds testing to explore the relationships among health expenditure, health outcomes, and economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2017. Their findings indicate a unidirectional causality running from health expenditure to infant mortality, with no causality observed between real GDP and infant mortality. Additionally, they identified a unidirectional causal relationship from health expenditure and real GDP to both life expectancy and maternal mortality, as well as a unidirectional causality from real GDP to health expenditure. The study concludes that health expenditure and economic growth are critical determinants of health outcomes in Nigeria.

1.3 Methodology

The theoretical framework of this study is based on the Grossman theory of demand for health. Grossman's theory is based on the proposition of unconstrained utility maximization theory whereby individuals make choices about their health based on a combination of factors, including their health-related behaviours, investments in health capital, and the demand for medical care. The theory emphasises the relationship between healthcare spending and health outcomes. Following Ibrahim and Anthony (2020); Guoxin, et al (2022); Jacques and Noël (2024), Abbuy (2018); Shuangshuang *et al.* (2021); and Muiz and Emeka (2023), the model for the study is stated below with variance in the usage of variables.

$$HO = f(\text{Gini}, \text{OOP}, \text{HeaEx}, \text{GDPpc}) \quad (1)$$

Where:

HO = Health outcome

Gini = Gini index

OOP = Out-of-Pocket health expenditure

HeaEx = Health expenditure

GDPpc = Gross domestic product per capita

Equation 1 above can be expressed in the econometric form as:

$$\log U_{5\text{Mor}} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \log \text{Gini}_{it} + \beta_2 \log \text{OOP}_{it} + \beta_3 \log \text{HeaEx}_{it} + \beta_4 \log \text{GDPpc}_{it} + (\theta_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}) \quad (2)$$

Table 1: Variables, Measurement, Source & A priori Expectation

S/N	Variables	Measurement	Source	A priori Expectation
1.	Gini index (Gini)	Pre-tax national income (top 10%)	World Income Inequality Database (WIID)	It is expected that income inequality (proxy by Gini index) will have positive relationship with U_5 mortality.
2.	Out-of-Pocket health expenditure (OOP)	Out-of-pocket expenditure per capita, PPP (current international \$)	World Bank's World Development Indicators	It is expected that Out-of-Pocket health expenditure (OOP) will have an inverse effect on U_5 mortality.
3.	Health expenditure (HeaEx)	Domestic general government health expenditure per capita, PPP (current international \$)	World Bank's World Development Indicators	It is expected that Health expenditure (HeaEx) will have an inverse effect on U_5 mortality.
4.	GDP per capita (GDPpc)	GDP per capita, PPP (current international \$)	World Bank's World Development Indicators	It is expected that GDP per capita (GDPpc) will have an inverse effect on U_5 mortality.

Equation 2 follows the fixed effect model given the outcome of our Hausman test. In the equation (2), U_{5Mor} is the Under-5 mortality representing the dependent variable; $(\theta_{it} + \epsilon_{it})$ represent the composition of the error term for the individual countries' specific random effect (θ_{it}) and the error that varies both in individual countries and over time (ϵ_{it}). To take advantage of the possibility of simultaneous estimation of the short and long run dynamics with accommodation of different orders of integration, which consequently is prone to fewer issues of endogeneity, we convert the model above to ARDL-PMG. Thus, we transform it into an error correction format as shown below:

$$\Delta \log U_{5Mor,it} = \varphi_i (\log U_{5Mor,it-1} - \lambda_1 \log Gini_{it} - \lambda_2 \log OOP_{it} - \lambda_3 \log HeaEx_{it} - \lambda_4 \log GDPpc_{it}) + \sum_{p=1}^{p-1} \phi \Delta \log U_{5Mor,it-1} + \sum_{q=1}^{q-1} \beta_{1i} \Delta \log Gini_{it-q} + \sum_{q=1}^{q-1} \beta_{2i} \Delta \log OOP_{it-q} + \sum_{q=1}^{q-1} \beta_{3i} \Delta \log HeaEx_{it-q} + \sum_{q=1}^{q-1} \beta_{4i} \Delta \log GDPpc_{it-q} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

Equation 3 above is similar to Engle and Granger (1987) and it is referred to as linear ARDL. In the model, $\Delta \log U_{5Mor,it}$ is the dependent variable representing change in log of Under-5 mortality for country i at time t . The first block in the right side of the model, (comprising φ_i , $\log U_{5Mor,it-1}$, $\lambda_1 \log Gini_{it}$, $\lambda_2 \log OOP_{it}$, $\lambda_3 \log HeaEx_{it}$, and $\lambda_4 \log GDPpc_{it}$) represents error correction term. φ_i is the group-specific speed of adjustment coefficient (it is expected that $\varphi_i < 0$ and its $\rho < 0.05$). $\log U_{5Mor,it-1}$ is the lagged Under-5 mortality. $\lambda_1 \log Gini_{it}$ is the long run coefficient of Gini index (income inequality); $\lambda_2 \log OOP_{it}$ the long run coefficient of out-of-pocket health expenditure; $\lambda_3 \log HeaEx_{it}$ is the long run coefficient of domestic general government health per capita; and $\lambda_4 \log GDPpc_{it}$ is the long run coefficient of gross domestic product per capita. In the second block of the model's right-hand side, we have short-run dynamic coefficients of changes in Gini, OOP, HeaEx and GDP per capita. The post estimation tests include serial correlation LM test, functional form (RESET), heteroskedasticity test, and CUSUM.

To empirically analyze, we collected cross-sectional data for the five biggest African economies comprising South Africa, Egypt, Algeria, Nigeria and Ethiopia from 2000 to 2023. The variables in our analysis include under-5 mortality, income inequality (proxy by Gini index), Out-of-Pocket Health expenditure (proxy by domestic general government health per capita), and GDP per capita.

1.4 Results and Discussion

First, the study employed two panel unit root tests, as shown in Table 1, to confirm the stationarity of the employed variables. For this purpose, we applied Levin, Lin, and Chin (LLC), Im, Pesaran and Shin (IPS). The result for $\log U_{5mor}$ shows that both the LLC and IPS tests are stationarity at levels (I(0)). The result for $\log OOP$ is stationary after the first difference (I(1)) for both the LLC and IPS. The result for $\log HeaEx$ is stationary at level (I(0)) for LLC but after the first difference (I(1)) for IPS. The results for $\ln Gini_index$ and $\ln GDPpc$ are stationary at levels (I(0)) for both LLC and IPS. Thus, there is a mixed order $\{(I(0)) \& (I(1))\}$ which guarantees the adoption of panel ARDL-PMG methodology, applying Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) for appropriate number of lags.

Table 2: Unit root test

	LLC			IPS		
	I(0)	I(1)	Decision	I(0)	I(1)	Decision
logU_5mor	5.44756	-	I(0)	-2.62765	-	I(0)
logOOP	3.03457	-5.04553	I(1)	-1.18805	-4.9898	I(1)
logHeaEx	2.83692	-	I(0)	-0.73198	-5.2213	I(1)
logGini_index	3.02412	-	I(0)	-2.56765	-	I(0)
logGDPpc	4.43997	-	I(0)	-3.21628	-	I(0)

Source: Authors' computation (2024)

To investigate the effect of income inequality and OOP on health outcomes, the study applies panel ARDL-PMG, as reported in Table 2. The long run estimate indicates that income inequality (proxy by logGini_index) has a positive and significant effect with a coefficient of 1.964752 and the ρ -value of 0.0008 overall. This implies that a 1% increase in income inequality leads to a 1.96% increase in the dependent variable overall, suggesting that as inequality widens in the countries under study, health outcomes worsen, potentially due to unequal access to healthcare services and other socio-economic opportunities in those countries. Odusanya supports this outcome *et al.* (2021), Shuangshuang *et al.* (2021), Lawal, Isik and Abdul (2020). It contradicts Orekoya (2022), Roman *et al.* (2019), who conclude that an increase in income inequality leads to a decrease in child mortality. However, in the short run, neither the current nor lagged changes in logGini_index show significant effects on the lnU_5mor, suggesting that the impact of inequality unfolds more gradually over time. Furthermore, logOOP also shows a positive and significant effect on health outcome (logU_5mor) with a coefficient of 0.452556 and the ρ -value of 0.0000. This suggests that as income disparities widen, poorer households face increased financial barriers to accessing healthcare, leading to higher child mortality rates. This agrees with Jacques and Noël (2024). This finding reflects the financial burden of healthcare costs on households, particularly in a context where healthcare systems may lack adequate public financing, consequently increasing Under_5 mortality. On the contrary, while the short logOOP shows a negative effect, such effect is statistically not significant, showing a coefficient of -0.026853 and the ρ -value of 0.6383.

Government health expenditure (logHeaExp) demonstrates a significant negative relationship with health outcome, with a coefficient of -0.320154 and ρ -value of 0.0000. This result indicates that a 1% increase in health expenditure reduces the dependent variable by 0.32% overall, showing that higher overall health expenditure improves health outcomes through increased funding for healthcare infrastructure, services, and programs. This finding aligns with Jacques *et al.* (2024), Odusanya *et al.* (2021), Muiz *et al.* (2023), Mohammad *et al.* (2022), and Uche (2020). It deviates from Adeagbo (2020), Michael *et al.* (2018), Aronu, *et al.* (2019) and Rezwanul *et al.* (2018), who

suggest a positive effect of public health expenditure on child mortality. In the short run, logHeaExp has a positive, insignificant effect on U_5mor with a coefficient of 0.011594 ρ -value of 0.1087. logGDPpc hurts health outcome with a coefficient of -0.361023 and the ρ -value of 0.0094. This implies that in the long run, a 1% increase in GDPpc reduces the dependent variable by 0.36%. The implication of this is that the economic growth in the studied countries contributes to better health outcomes by improving living standards, increasing access to essential services, and reducing poverty. Odusanya supports this *et al.* (2021), Mohammad, Nick, Nicholas, and Jeff (2020), Abbuy (2018), Damian and Chukwunonso (2014), and Micheal *et al.* (2018). However, it does not agree with Orekoya (2022). Like other variables, logGDPpc shows a negative, insignificant effect on U_5mor in the short run with the coefficient of -0.076517 and the ρ -value of 0.3224.

Other components of the table include the error correction term (ECT) represented by (COINTEQ01), which shows a negative coefficient value of -0.109981 and the ρ -value of 0.0270, suggesting that about 10.99% of the disequilibrium from the previous period is corrected in the current period, indicating a slow speed of adjustment toward long-run equilibrium. The one year lagged change in Under-5 Mortality (D(logGini_index)) has a positive coefficient 0.319773 and the ρ -value of 0.0058. This outcome reflects that a 1% increase in the previous period's under-5 mortality is associated with a 0.32% increase in the dependent variable in the short run. Finally, the constant term (C) is significant at coefficient of -0.104092 and ρ -value of 0.0316, representing baseline adjustments to the dependent variable when every variable in the model is zero.

Table 3: Short-run and long-run ARDL Estimates

Variable	ARDL-PMG			
	Coefficient	S.E	t-Stat	Prob.
Long run				
logGini_index	1.964752	0.557193	3.526164	0.0008
logOOP	0.452556	0.086688	5.220494	0.0000
logHeaEx	-0.320154	0.048292	-6.629544	0.0000
logGDPpc	-0.361023	0.134612	-2.681953	0.0094
Short run				
COINTEQ01	-0.109981	0.048527	-2.266357	0.0270
D(logU_5mor(-1))	0.319773	0.111846	2.859037	0.0058
D(logGini_index)	0.216759	0.260052	0.833520	0.4078
D(logGini_index(-1))	-0.200835	0.190972	-1.051644	0.2971
D(logOOP)	-0.013053	0.027628	-0.472472	0.6383
D(logOOP(-1))	-0.026853	0.009800	-2.740070	0.0080
D(logHeaExp)	0.011594	0.007123	1.627695	0.1087
D(logHeaExp(-1))	0.012213	0.007270	1.679902	0.0981
D(logGDPpc)	-0.076517	0.076702	-0.997588	0.3224
D(logGDPPC(-1))	0.223964	0.090868	2.464727	0.0165
C	-0.104092	0.047320	-2.199756	0.0316

Source: Authors' computation (2024)

1.5 Conclusion and Recommendation

The study examined the effect of income inequality and out-of-pocket health expenditure on health outcomes in the selected African economies, including Nigeria. Leveraging on the panel ARDL-PMG estimation technique, the results of the analysis show that none of the variables has a statistically significant effect on the health outcome in the short run, except the previous year lag of U_5 mortality. However, overall, both the Gini index and OOP demonstrate a positive significant effect on the U_5 mortality rate, while health expenditure and GDP per capita demonstrate a negative significant effect on the U_5 mortality rate. Thus, income inequality and out-of-pocket health expenditure have long-run impacts on health outcomes in the selected African countries. The study recommends measures to reduce income inequality, which could involve implementing progressive tax policies, providing social security programs, promoting human capital development initiatives via free education, and health care services. Besides, expansion of public funding expenditure and promotion of usage of healthcare insurance coverage for a larger

percentage of the population, subsidies and regulation of health costs, all aimed at alleviation of the burden of out-of-pocket health expenditure on the populace.

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